

SEMANTIC READING STRATEGIES AND WORKING WITH TEXT

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7480545>

ELSEVIER

Received: 22-12-2022

Accepted: 22-12-2022

Published: 22-12-2022

Sayitova Kamila Hasanovna

Bukhara engineering-technological institute

Abstract:

Keywords:...

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

The global processes of informatization of society - the increase in the amount of textual information every year, the presentation of new requirements for its analysis, systematization and processing speed determined the need to develop new approaches to learning. Teachers are faced with the task of preparing people capable of quickly perceiving text and processing large amounts of information, helping them master modern strategies, methods, and technologies. The key to the success of a modern person is the ability to extract the necessary information from various sources and use it effectively, therefore, today the problem of teaching reading is becoming relevant in the light of the modernization of general education. But over the past decades, there has been a decrease in interest in reading, the level of reading competence, which, of course, affects the results of schooling. The decline in interest in books and reading in connection with the development of the media is observed throughout the world. Semantic reading is a fairly new concept in pedagogy. According to the definition of A.A. Leontiev, semantic reading is the perception of graphically designed textual information and its processing into personal-semantic attitudes in accordance with the communicative-cognitive task.

Reading competence is a necessary condition for students to master almost all academic disciplines. The possession of semantic reading skills contributes to productive learning and helps to develop analytical, interpretive and critical thinking. When a child masters semantic reading, then he develops oral speech and, as a result, written speech. Meaningful reading should not be seen as a type of reading, but rather as a level of reading. The skill of working with text is an important component in the formation of information competence of students. One of the main ways to develop reading literacy is a strategic approach to teaching

meaningful reading. To work with the text at each stage, the reader chooses his own strategies.

Learning strategies are a set of actions that a learner takes to facilitate learning, make it more efficient, effective, faster, more enjoyable, and aim and bring learning activities closer to their own goals. If successful, the student remembers the ways of his actions, operations, resources used, transfers the strategy to other situations, makes it universal. The number of strategies and the frequency of their use are individual. The individual value of the strategy is realized by the individual. Thus, a strategy (in learning) is primarily a systematic plan, a program of actions and operations, consciously applied to manage learning in order to improve it.

Teaching reading strategies and the consistent application of reading strategies for different texts will allow the subject teacher to change the methodology of the lesson, to differentiate, individualize and intensify the learning process as much as possible, since most of the strategies provide for individual, pair work and work in small groups, including research. The use of reading strategies will give the work with the text a dialogue and interactive character, directly connect reading with other types of speech activity - speaking and writing. The implementation of this approach in daily educational practice changes the nature of working with text, making the reading process itself interactive. The student, in the process of mastering reading strategies, learns to control his understanding of the text. To successfully master the text, the student must master a set of techniques, strategies for working with textual information. The choice of strategies is individual, but in order to make a choice, the student must have a repertoire of strategies in his experience.

Strategy is not the simple application of one means on the basis of one rule. This is a group of actions and operations organized to achieve a goal, subordinate to the movement towards a common ultimate goal. N.N. Smetannikova offers the following types of strategies for working with informational text: pre-text activity strategies; text activity strategies; post-text strategies; vocabulary development strategy; text compression strategy; general educational strategies.

We will consider the concept of strategy as a plan-program of joint activities in which the student works independently under the guidance of a teacher. In the educational process, three strategies are mainly used: pre-text activity strategies; strategies of text activity strategy; post-text strategies.

Pre-text activity strategies are a fairly new phenomenon in the work of a teacher. Previously, this stage was limited to the "Read the text" task. The purpose of pretext strategies are: setting goals and objectives of reading; updating or familiarization with important concepts, terms, keywords; updating of previous knowledge; diagnostics; formation of a reading attitude with the help of questions or tasks; increasing the speed of reading and the number of readings; reader

motivation; inclusion of the mechanism of anticipation - prediction of content, thematic and emotional orientation; the formation of the ability and habit to think about a book before reading.

With the help of anticipation - a guess, a mental anticipation of the content and a plan for the subsequent presentation - the reader runs ahead in thought. He not only understands what the author is talking about in the text being read at the moment, but also assumes, guesses - according to the logic of the development of the author's thought - what he should say after this. The reader becomes a kind of collaborator. He himself "continues" the author's text, he mentally "writes" the continuation. Such a position causes high intellectual activity, does not allow losing the thread of presentation, the author's train of thought, helps to notice all deviations, all unexpected moves and shades, involuntarily sets in a critical mood in all cases of discrepancies between the author's guess and the actual train of thought.

Psychologist L.I. Kaplan notes that already reading the title of the text causes the desire to formulate something similar to a "hypothesis" about the further content. In such cases, the reading process takes on the character of a test of this assumption. Whether this "hypothesis" was justified or not, it always contributes to a better understanding of the text. The process of understanding is activated, became purposeful. By building a hypothesis, the reader draws on the stock of his knowledge on the subject. Thanks to this, he enters the circle of problems discussed in advance, and then actively compares what is expressed in the text with what he knows from his past experience. There are several types of anticipation: anticipation of the plan of subsequent presentation (it helps to control the composition of the work, to comprehend its logical structure); anticipation of the content of the subsequent presentation (it helps to correlate parts of the text according to content, to control meaningful connections in the text). If the author describes specific facts, then he leads the reader to their generalization, to the conclusion from them, and the reader anticipates this conclusion, guesses about it (anticipation of the conclusion). If the author has formulated a general position, said about any subject in a general form, then, after this, he will probably explain it, substantiate it, specify it. The reader expects clarification and, looking ahead, builds guesses about it (anticipation of justification). Anticipation forces you to correlate parts of the text according to content, to use your own knowledge to correctly understand the connections and relationships in the text. The result is high intellectual activity; the text is comprehended deeply and critically, which, in fact, was required.

Pre-reading questions. The questions that precede the presentation encourage the reader to look for an answer in the text, compare it with the question and with their own knowledge of the subject, i.e. activate mental activity. Questions usually

arise when there are difficult to understand, problematic places in the text. Questions are also raised about the general features of the text, in particular, logical and other errors in it (violations of evidence or consistency, complicated accessibility of presentation). The reason for the questions is also the natural limitation of the text: the thought in the text is not revealed immediately, but gradually and, being unfinished, prompts the question; the idea in the text is not fully disclosed, since what, in the author's opinion, is well known to the reader, is omitted.

Much will be given to the reader by questions related to the meaning and role of individual words. For example, is there really that relationship between the parts of the text that establishes the word that serves as a link between them. Especially important is the ability to notice, highlight the characteristic semantic details of the text, i.e. ability to its semantic microanalysis. It can rightly be regarded as one of the manifestations of such a valued criticality of the mind. From the position of awakening interest in reading, researchers note the following most productive pre-

"Brainstorm"- The goal of the strategy is to update previous knowledge and experience relevant to the topic of the text. Working process: What associations do you have about the stated topic?

The teacher writes down all the named associations. (Now let's read the text and see if the information you gave in the Brainstorm is adequate to what we learned from the text).

"Glossary". The goal of the strategy is to update and repeat the vocabulary associated with the topic of the text. Working process: We will read the informative text "When did cinema appear?" Look at the list of words and mark those that may be related to the text. (When you finish reading the text, go back to these words and look at their meaning and the use of words used in the text).

"Dissection of the Question". The goal of the strategy is a semantic guess about the possible content of the text based on its title.

Working process: Read the title of the text and divide it into semantic groups. What do you think the text will be about?

"Alphabet at the Round Table"-We plan to read and discuss the topic of the relationship between man and animals, man and nature. On the alphabet map provided to you, write the titles or authors of books that are related to this topic. The discussion of the results takes place according to the method of free discussion.

"Competing with a Writer". The goal is to motivate the person to read the book. Try to predict the content of the book by looking at the illustrations. One student offers his own version of the plot of the book, the rest supplement it. The goal is to understand the text and create its reader's interpretation.

Text Activity Strategies. The goals of strategies in the executive phase of reading are: development of its mechanisms, that is, putting forward a hypothesis

about the content of what is being read, its confirmation / rejection, contextual and semantic conjecture, reflection while reading about what and how I read and how well I understand what I read. The main principles of the strategies of this stage, the stage of text activity, are: stop activity, thinking out loud, forecast, the establishment of diverse and multidirectional connections and relationships in the course of the development of the plot. The teacher intervenes in the student's reading process in order to help, provide additional information and simply educate. The more difficult the material with which the reader works, the more help the teacher needs. Therefore, the most effective strategies will be those associated with keeping records in a variety of forms, with reading guides, with multiple options for working with a word.

Texting strategies include: "Reading in a circle" (alternate reading) "(goal: checking understanding of the text read aloud); "Reading to yourself with questions" (goal: to teach you to read the text thoughtfully, asking yourself more and more complicated questions); "Reading with stops" (goal: managing the process of comprehending the text while reading it); "Reading to yourself with notes" (goal: monitoring the understanding of the text being read and its critical analysis).

The development of semantic reading skills is also effectively facilitated by the use of critical thinking technology, the content of which is aimed at forming a thoughtful reader who is able to analyze, compare, contrast and evaluate familiar and new information. Technologies for the development of critical thinking, as well as strategies for the development of semantic reading, are aimed at forming a thoughtful reader who analyzes, compares, contrasts and evaluates familiar and new information. This technology is a system of strategies and methodological techniques designed for use in various subject areas, types and forms of work. It allows you to achieve such educational results as: ability to work with information flow in different fields of knowledge; the ability to express one's thoughts (orally and in writing) clearly, confidently, specifically in relation to others; the ability to develop one's own opinion on the basis of comprehension of various experiences, ideas and ideas; the ability to solve problems, the ability to independently engage in their own learning (academic mobility); the ability to cooperate and work in a group, the ability to build constructive relationships with other people.

A training session developed using the technology of critical thinking is built on the basis of three main stages, conditionally named - "challenge", "comprehension", "reflection".

"Challenge" - stimulating interest in new knowledge occurs through the "extraction" of what is already known on this topic and clarifying the questions that have arisen. The questions that have arisen raise the need for new knowledge. This

stage contributes to the emergence or strengthening of motivation in the knowledge of new material studied at the second stage.

“Comprehension” - students are presented with new material in the form of a text and the process of accepting new information by students is organized. There is an active acquisition and comprehension of new information. The main task is to maintain the activity, interest and momentum of movement created during the challenge stage. It is important to support students' efforts to track their own understanding. At this point, students consciously link the new with the already known. At this stage, critical and comparative analysis and synthesis are carried out.

"Reflection" - students' awareness of new knowledge, holistic understanding, appropriation and generalization of the information received; development of one's own attitude to the studied material. The student sees the meaning in his actions, correlates them with the result, realizes the experience gained. The features of the technology lie in the fact that students are placed in a situation of independent work with information presented in the form of a text that needs to be perceived, ranked by novelty and significance, creatively interpreted, made predictions, conclusions and generalizations. It gives students a tool that teaches them how to work independently with new information.

Thus, working with a book (with a text) is a specific system of skills that everyone can and should master. Individual differences and abilities play an important role, but the basis of working with the book is made up of specific actions and operations that are available to each person. These actions and operations include: operations of semantic perception of text elements; understanding of words, sentences, paragraphs; understanding of what (about which subjects) the text says (and the ability to draw up a plan on this basis), and what exactly is said about it (and the ability to make extracts and draw up abstracts on this basis), i.e. understanding the main judgments (statements) of the text; understanding how the subjects are logically connected in the text and the ability, on the basis of this, to draw up a graph diagram of its main content; understanding the main idea of the text and its subtext; understanding how the content of a given text is related to the content of other studied texts (and on this basis, the interpretation of the text).

The above operations underlie the possession of semantic (learning) reading - the main type of reading as part of educational activity, the result of which is a deep, comprehensive understanding of educational information (text). To master this type of reading, it is necessary to master the methods of understanding (comprehension) of the educational text.

REFERENCES:

1. Davey B. Using textbook activity guides to help students learn from textbooks / B. Davey // Journal of Reading. – 1986. – № 29. – P. 17-23.
2. Бондаренко, С.М. Как учить работать с книгой / С.М. Бондаренко, Г.Г. Граник, Л.А. Концева.- М.: Просвещение, 1995.
3. Гальперин, И.Р. Текст как объект лингвистического исследования / И.Р. Гальперин. – М.: Наука, 1981.
4. Куропятник И.В. Чтение как стратегически важная компетентность для молодых людей // Педагогическая мастерская. Все для учителя. - 2012. - № 64.
5. Сайитова Комила Хасановна. Применение наглядных методов в процессе обучения и воспитания // Достижения науки и образования. 2019. №5 (46). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/primenie-naglyadnyh-metodov-v-protssesse-obucheniya-i-vospitaniya>.
6. Khudoyberdievna, Saidova Zulfizar. "English phraseology and its integration with terminology." ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL 11.2 (2021): 1618-1622. <https://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:aca&volume=11&issue=2&article=265>.
7. Сайитова Комила Хасановна Деятельность преподавателя в учебном процессе // Достижения науки и образования. 2017. №5 (18). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/deyatelnost-prepodavatelya-v-uchebnom>
8. Sayitova, K. H. (2020). The role of personality-oriented approach in the process of education. Theoretical & Applied Science, (3), 190-192. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=42658844>.
9. Sayitova Komila Hasanovna The importance of country research material in the development of speech habits // Достижения науки и образования. 2017. №5 (18). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-importance-of-country-research-material-in-the-development-of-speech-habits>.
10. K.H.Sayitova.PSYCHOLINGUISTIC ASPECT OF STUDYING THE PROBLEM OF BILINGUISM. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal 2 (11), 219-226. <https://wos.academiascience.org/index.php/wos/article/view/448/421>.
11. K.H.Sayitova Methods of Artistic Translation of Comparisons On the Example of the Story of E. Hemingway Old Man and the Sea. International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development. <https://archive.org/details/httpswww.ijtsrd.com/engineering/other/38741/methods-of-artistic-translation-of-compa>.

12. Sayitova, K. H. (2020). USING TECHNIQUES AND METHODS OF THE CLIL SYSTEM IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING ENGLISH. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (3), 380-382. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=42658876>.
13. Hasanovna, S. K., & Nargiza, N. (2019). The advantages of teaching grammar through games. *Достижения науки и образования*, (6 (47)), 30-31. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-advantages-of-teaching-grammar-through-games>.
14. Hasanovna, S. K. (2018). Advantages of using brainstormers at English classes. *Проблемы педагогики*, (2 (34)), 55-56. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/advantages-of-using-brainstormers-at-english-classes>.
15. Hasanovna, S. K. (2017). The importance of country research material in the development of speech habits. *Достижения науки и образования*, (5 (18)), 59-60. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-importance-of-country-research-material-in-the-development-of-speech-habits>.
16. Sayitova, K. H. (2019). THE ADVANTAGES OF TEACHING GRAMMAR THROUGH GAMES Sayitova KH, Narziyeva N. 2. *Достижения науки и образования*,30.<https://staff.tiiame.uz/storage/users/85/articles/WR4kpbreVVXtEFSxD7lx8f7paIUkE0jbpZP6sqkI.pdf#page=31>.
17. Djumayeva, N. (2021, March). THE MAGIC ITEM PRESENTED BY FAIRIES IN ENGLISH FAIRY TALES. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 249-250). <https://papers.econferenceglobe.com/index.php/ecg/article/view/97>.
18. Джумаева, Н. Д. (2018). The peculiarities of magical objects in English folklore. *Молодой ученый*, (9), 194-196. <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=32555941>.
19. Djumayeva, N. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MAGICAL JEWELLERY AND ORNAMENTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK FAIRY TALES. *JournalNX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal* . ISSN No: 2581 - 4230.VOLUME 7, ISSUE6, June. -2021,138-142. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/347771-comparative-analysis-of-magical-jeweller-8838f05c.pdf>.
20. Zulfizar Khudoyberdievna, S. . (2022). THE MAIN FEATURES OF TRANSLATION OF PHRASEOLOGY FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(3), 523-526. <http://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/ni/article/view/1024>.
21. Kobilova Aziza Bakhridinova 2022. Semantic and Lingua-Cultural Features of English and Uzbek Medical Periphrases. *International Journal on Integrated Education*. 5, 6 (Jun. 2022), 162-167. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.31149/ijie.v5i6.3144>.

22. Zarifovna, R. N. (2022). Types of euphemisms used in everyday life. Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes, 86–89. Retrieved from <http://conferenceseries.info/index.php/online/article/view/52>.

23. Расулов, З. И. (2017). Особенности моделирования эллиптических предложений в связи с позиционными звеньями. Тил бирликларини қиёсий-типологик ва лингвомаданиятшунослик йўналишларида тадқиқи ва уларнинг тилларни ўқитишдаги ўрни. Илмий мақолалар тўплами. Қ, 2, 54-56. Тил бирликларини қиёсий-типологик ва лингвомаданиятшунослик йўналишларида тадқиқи ва уларнинг тилларни ўқитишдаги ўрни. Илмий мақолалар тўплами. Қ, 2, 54-56.

https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cluster=17941465232623595948&hl=en&as_sdt=2005&scioldt=0,5.

24. Izomovich, R. Z., & Shavkatovich, S. X. UDC: 82 REDUCTION AS THE WAY OF THE LANGUAGE ECONOMY MANIFESTATION. SCIENTIFIC REPORTS OF BUKHARA STATE UNIVERSITY, 68(15), 41-44. https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/2943/1845.

25. Rasulov, Z. I. THE PROBLEM OF LANGUAGE ECONOMY FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF LANGUAGE EVOLUTION. https://uniwork.buxdu.uz/resurs/14162_1_335A013FB811809E768BB3EC8D34729184AA276D.pdf.